

A Framework for Evaluating Large-Scale Resource Recovery Strategies to Achieve Compliance with Directive (EU) 2024/3019

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Abstract

This study proposes an integrated experimental and modeling framework to evaluate the feasibility and impact of utilizing volatile fatty acids (VFAs) derived from primary sludge as a sustainable carbon source to enhance biological nitrogen removal under Directive (EU) 2024/3019. The directive imposes strict nitrogen effluent limits and emphasizes resource recovery, necessitating innovative strategies in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). While VFA-based strategies demonstrate potential, real-scale implementation faces significant challenges, particularly due to variability in fermentate production caused by fluctuations in sludge composition, operational conditions, and environmental factors. These inconsistencies can compromise VFA quality and denitrification performance. Scenario analyses conducted at 15°C, a critical low-temperature condition, were used to assess effluent TN concentrations under different operational strategies. Compliance with the 10 mg/L TN target was demonstrated by maintaining an optimized sludge retention time (SRT) of 25 days and a fermentate flow rate of approximately 75 m³/d, albeit with increased energy costs of 600 kWh/day (60 Euros/day) to achieve a 12% improvement in denitrification efficiency. We highlight the complexity of implementing resource recovery strategies at scale and the need for further research and operational adaptations to align with regulatory goals.

Keywords: Biological Nitrogen Removal, Resource Recovery, Activated Sludge Model, Temperature-Phased Anaerobic Digestion (TPAD), Volatile Fatty Acids (VFAs), Directive (EU) 2024/3019

INTRODUCTION

Eutrophication in marine and freshwater environments, primarily driven by excessive nitrogen discharges, poses significant ecological concerns. In response, Directive (EU) 2024/3019 has established more stringent total nitrogen (TN) effluent requirements for wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). Specifically, facilities serving agglomerations of 10,000 to 150,000 population equivalents (p.e.) must achieve TN concentrations below 10 mg/L, while those treating over 150,000 p.e. must meet an 8 mg/L limit, alongside an 80% reduction in nitrogen loads relative to influent levels (Annex I, Table 2). Beyond nutrient removal, the directive emphasizes circular economy principles, mandating that WWTPs recover valuable resources such as carbon and energy and minimize greenhouse gas emissions. These requirements seek to modernize the urban wastewater sector by integrating energy efficiency, operational cost savings, and resource recovery objectives with improved nutrient-removal performance. Biological denitrification, a widely adopted process in activated sludge systems, is central to meeting the directive's nitrogen removal targets. However, denitrification often encounters limitations due to insufficient biodegradable carbon in the influent. Utilities commonly rely on exogenous carbon sources (e.g., methanol, ethanol, or acetate) to offset this shortfall, which entails high costs, safety concerns, and additional environmental impacts. Therefore, identifying sustainable alternative carbon sources is pivotal to achieving compliance with Directive (EU) 2024/3019 while advancing circular economy goals (Borzooei et al. 2024). Volatile fatty acids (VFAs), generated through the anaerobic degradation of primary and secondary sludge, represent a dual opportunity for advancing resource recovery goals and enhancing biological denitrification processes under stringent nitrogen removal targets. Although VFAs have demonstrated efficacy as supplemental carbon, their large-scale application and integration within WWTPs under the directive's enhanced regulatory framework remain insufficiently explored (Feng et al. 2022).

Accordingly, this study investigates the feasibility of TPAD for generating VFAs from primary sludge (PS), subsequently used as an internal carbon source in anoxic zones. Conducted at a WWTP in Italy, the research assesses whether VFA production via TPAD can help facilities comply with TN discharge standards while improving operational efficiency and resource recovery. The combined laboratory- and pilot-scale evaluations, supported by advanced process modeling, aim to provide strategic insights for WWTPs seeking to meet stringent nitrogen limits and support broader sustainability objectives envisioned under Directive (EU) 2024/3019.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted at a municipal WWTP in the northwest of Italy. A comprehensive account of the WWTP's layout and operating parameters is available from previous research (Borzooei et al. 2019b).

2.1 Temperature-Phased Anaerobic Digestion

PS was subjected to TPAD in three continuous stirred-tank reactors (CSTRs) to evaluate VFA production and sludge biodegradability under distinct thermal regimes. Two laboratory-scale reactors, called Digesters A and B, each with a working volume of 9 L, were operated in series. Digester A was maintained at 55°C (thermophilic conditions) with a hydraulic retention time (HRT) of 2 days, while Digester B operated at 38°C (mesophilic conditions) with a 20-day HRT. Additionally, a larger mesophilic reactor (Digester C) with a 240-L working volume was included to assess scalability; it was also maintained at 38°C, with an HRT of 20 days. A detailed description of the experimental apparatus and the analyses performed on the sludge before and after the treatments are reported in previous research (Campo G. et al., 2024).

2.2 Characterization of Digestate Biodegradability

A series of respirometric and physicochemical procedures was implemented to characterize the digestate's organic composition and biodegradability. Soluble COD (COD_s) was determined using a three-stage filtration process (0.8 µm, 0.45 µm, 0.2 µm) after a 1:10 dilution. Respirometric assays included single-OUR tests performed on a 1.4-L sample of return-activated sludge (RAS) containing allylthiourea (ATU) to inhibit nitrification, thereby focusing on heterotrophic oxygen uptake. Multiple-OUR tests were also conducted, starting with a predetermined food-to-microorganism (F/M) ratio to evaluate extended biodegradation dynamics over an established test duration. Following standard respirometric procedures (Borzooei et al. 2021), data from these OUR tests were analyzed using the trapezoidal integration method and an assumed heterotrophic yield coefficient (Y_H) to assess the readily and slowly biodegradable COD fractions.

2.3 Process Model Development, Calibration, and COD Mass Balance Analysis

A process simulation model was developed and calibrated to evaluate the potential integration of fermented digestate into the WWTP's treatment train. This model reproduced the plant's operational units, including the primary clarifier, anoxic and aerobic bioreactors, secondary clarification, and effluent discharge and incorporated an influent batch unit for digestate addition. Calibration was performed using targeted measurements and sampling data obtained at the half-module scale, ensuring accurate reflection of site-specific hydraulic and biological processes. Further details on model development and calibration are provided by Borzooei et al. (2019a). To quantify the fermentate production capacity of the plant under the concurrent operational scheme and COD distribution, a detailed mass balance was conducted based on pilot-scale digestate characterization. Measured parameters included total and COD_s, VFAs, and volatile suspended solids, enabling the estimation of how much COD was converted to methane or retained in the liquid fraction. Although mechanical pre-thickening was not implemented at the pilot stage, separation efficiency was assumed in addition to conversion rates in the mass. This assumption allowed for partitioning the liquid and solid fractions after thermophilic digestion, thus clarifying the potential volume of VFAs available as a supplemental carbon source.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Results from the mesophilic AD of PS indicate a specific methane production (SMP) of $0.264 \text{ Nm}^3 \text{ CH}_4/\text{kg VS}$ at 38°C with a 20-day HRT. Under TPAD, the overall SMP remained similar ($0.265 \text{ Nm}^3 \text{ CH}_4/\text{kg VS}$). Within the thermophilic phase at 55°C (HRT = 3 days), methane production was notably lower ($0.021 \text{ Nm}^3 \text{ CH}_4/\text{kg VS}$), yet approximately 15% of the incoming COD was transformed into VFAs. This relatively modest enhancement in total biogas underscores the key benefit of thermophilic fermentation for VFA production rather than elevated methane yields. Over the 120-day test, higher methane production generally coincided with diminished VFA concentrations, reflecting preferential consumption of VFAs by methanogenic communities. Fluctuations in VFA composition primarily involving acetic, propionic, and butyric acids highlighted the dynamic equilibrium of organic acid formation and consumption during TPAD operation. Respirometric assays on the fermented digestate showed that approximately 15.2% of total COD (i.e., $7150 \pm 85 \text{ mg/L}$) was readily biodegradable. Additional multiple-OUR tests revealed an extended biodegradation period over 25 hours, yielding a biodegradable COD (BCOD) fraction of $10135 \pm 22 \text{ mg/L}$, about 22% of the total COD. Notably, filtration reduced colloidal content to just 2% of the original sample, supporting the digestate's suitability as a supplemental carbon source in downstream biological processes.

A COD mass balance was performed using measured sludge characteristics. PS entered the thermophilic reactor at 4.17% COD (3590.4 kg COD/h) and was partially converted to methane (114.4 kg COD/h) and VFAs. After digestion, the fermentate (3476.2 kg COD/h) underwent an assumed mechanical pre-thickening step ($\eta = 97\%$ efficiency), resulting in a liquid fraction containing 227.8 kg COD/h of VFAs and a solid fraction (3034.6 kg COD/h) directed to mesophilic digestion. In this second stage, methane generation reached $41.95 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{h}$, with a substantial portion of non-biodegradable COD stabilized. Extrapolation of these findings suggests that each half-module of the plant could produce up to $150 \text{ m}^3/\text{d}$ of VFA-rich liquid; scaled to the entire facility, this capacity could increase up to $1200 \text{ m}^3/\text{d}$.

Finally, a series of dynamic simulations, implemented via simulation software, to assess various digestate feed rates under different SRT regimes (10–40 days) and wastewater temperature scenarios ($10\text{--}30^\circ\text{C}$). A proportional-integral (PI) controller regulated the waste-activated sludge (WAS) flow to maintain specific SRTs, while the α -factor (ratio of process water to clean water mass transfer coefficients) was adjusted to account for the influence of SRT on aeration (Borzooei et al., 2019).

Figures 1a and 1b present scenario-based analyses of WWTP performance, contrasting the impacts of modified operational configurations with current practices, particularly under challenging low-temperature conditions.

Figure 1. Results of the model-based Scenario Analysis (a) Electrical Energy Consumption Gap and (b) Effluent TN Differential under various combinations of SRT and fermentate flow rates at 15°C

The scenario analysis was designed to generate different performance assessment criteria, including TN concentration and mass flow in the effluent, denitrification rates in anoxic zones, total energy consumption, and energy production. Among these, the energy consumption gap and TN differential were chosen as key indicators to highlight the effect of resource recovery on plant

performance. Figure 1a shows the Electrical Energy Consumption Gap (kWh/d), while Figure 1b presents the Effluent TN Differential (kg TN/d) across various SRT and fermentate flow rate combinations. The red dashed lines in the figures represent critical operational benchmarks: an SRT of 25 days, identified in a previous study as optimal for overall system performance, and a TN concentration of 10 mg/L, which the plant manager highlighted as a challenging target under low-temperature conditions (15°C). This temperature was selected based on operational challenges during winter and extreme wet weather conditions, exacerbating the difficulty of maintaining compliance with the TN=10 mg/L limit. The scenario analysis results also confirmed that achieving the stricter TN=8 mg/L target is unfeasible due to the limitations of fermentate availability, even when strategies such as increasing the internal mixed liquor flow rate were tested.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study provides an integrated experimental and modeling framework for assessing the application of volatile fatty acids (VFAs) derived from primary sludge as a sustainable carbon source to enhance biological nitrogen removal in compliance with Directive (EU) 2024/3019. Our findings highlight several challenges and opportunities in implementing VFA-based strategies. Implementing VFA-based strategies at a real scale presents challenges, particularly due to variability in fermentate production arising from fluctuations in sludge composition, operational dynamics, and environmental conditions. These variations directly impact the quality and quantity of VFAs, potentially affecting denitrification performance. The scenario analysis, conducted under challenging temperature conditions of 15°C, revealed that achieving effluent TN concentrations below the directive's 8 mg/L target is unattainable given the current fermentate flow rate limitations. However, maintaining an SRT of 25 days, identified as optimal from previous studies alongside a fermentate flow rate of approximately 75 m³/d, enables compliance with the 10 mg/L TN limit, albeit at the cost of increased energy consumption. Specifically, an additional 600 kWh/day (equivalent to 60 Euros/day) is required to achieve a 12% improvement in denitrification efficiency under these conditions.

5. REFERENCES

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